

THINKING AND LOGICAL THINKING AS A FACTOR OF SPEECH CULTURE OF A PEDAGOGIC PERSON

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Abstract. One of the most important aspects of the 21st century, globalization, is vividly evident in the critical areas of national societies: social, economic, environmental and cultural processes. The foundation of globalization is formed by the international integration of the social, economic, and cultural activities of national state structures. The rapid development of information technologies has further accelerated the process of international integration, leading to its global significance.

Keywords: process, globalization, globalization process, etymology of the concept of “globalization”, genesis of the concept of “globalization”, theoretical description of the concept of “globalization”.

In the modern conditions of globalization, the following are required of a teacher: 1. Physical and mental health. 2. High moral and human qualities. 3. Deep and comprehensive knowledge in his/her main specialty. 4. Methodological perfection and professional competence. 5. Speech culture and spelling literacy 6. Constant self-improvement and professional development, etc.

In the process of studying the above requirements and the current state of the problem, we tried to further clarify the factors of speech culture and spelling literacy of the future teacher.

Usually, most teachers see their task in teaching and educating a person as equipping the student with the appropriate knowledge, skills and qualifications within the framework of their subject, forming in them the qualities of analysis, generalization and comparison. However, the work of a teacher and his/her pedagogical activity is wide-ranging. It is responsible for fulfilling the three important social functions of teaching - teaching, upbringing and personal development. However, classes in higher pedagogical institutions are not sufficiently connected with the practical and pedagogical activities of the teacher. This opinion can be explained by the following: First, the content of most of the classes included in the curriculum with the aim of preparing future teachers for creative activity is aimed precisely at forming the personality of the teacher. Although this situation has a positive effect on the formation of a teacher as a qualified specialist, it does not serve to master the methods of preparing for creative activity that he can directly apply in his professional and pedagogical activities. Second, in the preparation of future teachers for professional activity, the concept of creativity is interpreted in a certain limited sense, usually in the sense of preparing

for the implementation and management of technical creativity. Today, as a result of the global transformation of language teaching, traditional grammatical approaches are being replaced by communicative and sociocultural competencies. The theoretical foundations and methodological tools developed in world practice suggest that the person being formed in the educational process should be formed not only in terms of technical or artistic creativity, but also in terms of research creativity, which requires deeper knowledge [1].

Before considering the teacher's speech culture, oratory, and ability to express his thoughts orally and in writing, it is necessary to recall some information about language and speech.

Speech culture is an extremely important integral part of the life and culture of society, a certain reality, and a manifestation of special importance. It includes everyday, constant, necessary processes such as exchange of ideas, communication, and speech, "controls" them, through which they become reality, and has the power to influence. Language and speech are phenomena that demonstrate the dialectics of essence and phenomenon, generality and specificity. Language is manifested through speech as a generalization. Speech is the product of the use and activation of language units based on existing rules. Language and speech are dialectically interconnected socio-historical, socio-psychological phenomena, language exists as a means of communication, and speech as a method of communication. Speech is the process of using a unique socio-individual tool called language, the manifestation of language units and their capabilities in a necessary, constant relationship with objective existence, thinking, logical reasoning, and the situation. Speech is an official language. It is formed in a broad sense from words, word combinations and sayings. Naturally, each of these languages is a cherished language for a certain people. Each language has its own place in the upbringing of a person's thought.

The concept of striving for cultural speech has existed among all peoples since ancient times. This concept is a concept associated with certain linguistic norms, ethical and aesthetic requirements. Thus, the concept of speech. culture is an ethical and aesthetic category, a phenomenon that determines (indicates) the spirituality of each national language and nation.

Speech culture is not only an effort aimed at the conscious and purposeful regulation (processing and enrichment) of the literary language, but also an activity that serves to raise the general culture of the nation, to cultivate a certain "language taste" in people. When it comes to studying speech culture, it is considered to be the development of linguistic competence, the development of thinking operations, and in some cases, many researchers also pay special attention to the improvement of logical thinking. The higher the level of the attitude of the representatives of the language to the possibilities of this unique tool, other factors in its use: thinking, consciousness, being, various situations and circumstances, attitude to the goal, the higher the level of speech culture.

On the contrary, it is inevitable that the level of speech culture will be low. Teacher L.F. Voronina, unlike other pedagogical researchers, defines the process of linguistic competence as follows: “Mastering logical forms of thinking is maturity in thinking. Developed visual schematic thinking leads a person to a logical state. After mastering linguistic competence, visual assessment does not lose its meaning” [2]. That is, the author emphasizes the high role of the visual channel in well-understood and understandable situations and circumstances through these words.

Many scholars who have conducted research in the field of philology believe that linguistic competence is a set of concepts, conclusions inherent in the rules and laws of logic, which are formed through a conscious understanding of tasks.

Speaking of thinking and logical thinking, knowledge, in the ideas of the American psychologist, philosopher and educator J. Dewey, the child follows the path of humanity in knowledge, the assimilation of knowledge is an uncontrollable process, and the child assimilates educational material as a result of satisfying the need that has arisen in him. That is, the conditions for the effectiveness of teaching, the problematization of educational material should be associated with the activity of the child. In this regard, S.L. Rubinstein's idea that “Thinking begins with a problematic situation” is extremely important and has gained further recognition.

N.F. In his textbook "Pedagogical Psychology", Talizina singles out the following main thinking operations, which are widely used for logical thinking [3]:

- analysis and selection;
- comparison;
- abstraction;
- generalization;
- concretization, etc.

The term “speech culture” denotes three phenomena in linguistics: 1) the name of a cultural speech, that is, a speech phenomenon; 2) the name of a scientific problem related to the concept of cultural speech and called speech culture; 3) the name of the field, the department of linguistics, that studies the problems of speech culture.

Each of the three phenomena mentioned has its own complex forms and facets, and they should not be confused with each other.

Thus, the most important definitions given to speech culture are the following:
1. Speech culture is one of the distinctive features of the development of the literary language. 2. Speech culture (language culture) is an activity that consists in assisting in the formation and refinement of the norms of the literary language, that is, conscious intervention in the development of the language. 3. Speech culture is the skill of consciously perceiving the language, its laws and rules, and of constructing clear, clear, and expressive speech. 4. Speech culture is the complete and deep thinking of people among themselves, the thorough mastery of all the

possibilities and means of the language. 5. Speech culture is not only correct speech, but also readability and eloquence. 6. Speech culture is the art of speaking and writing in a purposeful manner, using language tools appropriately. 7. Speech culture is, first of all, a culture of thinking. 8. Speech is a cultural speech that is also distinguished by its national identity.

In conclusion, speech culture is an attitude towards the use of language, a tool of communication and interaction. The higher the level of the representatives of the language, the higher the level of speech culture. If, on the contrary, then speech culture is inevitably at a low level.

Speaking about speech culture, of course, there is also a debate about the appropriate and inappropriate use of words in speech. When calling a used language unit correct or incorrect, of course, it is necessary to base it on a certain criterion (criterion). This criterion (criterion) is called the literary language norm in linguistics.

The following special norms are distinguished: 1. Dialectal norm. 2. Colloquial speech norm. 3. Slang, jargon norm. 4. Literary language norm (literary norm).

The following lexical - semantic, pronunciation (ortho-epic), writing (graphics), phonetic, accentological (correct use of stress), grammatical (morphological and syntactic), word formation, spelling, stylistic and punctuation norms of the Uzbek literary language are distinguished.

There are oral and written forms of the literary norm, and if folk humorists, folk poets-bakhshis made a great contribution to the development of the oral literary norm, then the service of written literature, which is written down on the basis of the established writing form, is unlimited in the formation of the written literary norm. In general, the study of the literary language norm is not a new phenomenon. The language norm and the literary norm were studied as a problem even before the culture of speech was recognized as a scientific field. The literary language norm, the laws of its formation, development, and stabilization are the object of study of the field of speech culture.

The approach of the field of speech culture to the literary language norm differs from the grammatical approach in the following features:

a) speech culture should find the features that cause speech defects that change and deteriorate in the literary language norm and strive to correct them; b) speech culture should examine the norms of the literary language as a constantly developing and changing phenomenon and take into account new situations in the system of literary language norms, changing, modified situations, as well as "dead" situations that have gone out of use; c) speech culture should identify contradictory situations in the system of literary language norms and examine them at all levels of the language.

As is known, the emergence and development of language is inextricably linked with the development of society. It is a social phenomenon that arises in the process of social development, labor activity, and exists only in society, among people. As society develops, language also takes shape. Thus, the spirituality of the nation speaking this language increases, and its speech skills increase. Otherwise, the language will decline. This leads to the fading of speech skills and the impoverishment of spirituality.

Each person living in society is considered to be a separate speaker. The teacher is no exception. However, the speech tool common to all of them is the single language of this society.

A person acquires speech skills in speech activity, having a thorough knowledge of the rules of literary language culture, especially through reading fiction, newspapers and magazines, watching radio and television, in general, through information from the mass media and as a result of constant independent study.

Only a person who has deeply mastered the culture of the literary language will have a professional speech culture. In mastering the culture of the literary language, attention to the language, genuine love and respect for it are of great importance. The teacher must speak in the literary language. The literary language and its norms cannot be mastered simply by interest or by engaging in it in name only.

Human speech activity is manifested in three forms: speaking, reading and listening. When speaking, it is understood that the speaker gives information, advises, orders, asks about things unknown to him. When speaking, the speaker's knowledge, culture, ethics, and manners are revealed. There are monological and dialogical forms of speech.

Reading is the student's communication with the author of the work and the images he created through written speech. Thanks to reading, he becomes aware of the events reflected in the written speech.

A certain form of a text formed by a speaker or writer is an expression, which is not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also a phenomenon of spirituality and sophistication. Therefore, when it comes to a good speech, it is meant that the intended purpose reaches the listener or reader completely and clearly, and has a certain effect on them. Accordingly, certain requirements are placed on the speech. These requirements are the communicative qualities of speech, which include that the speech should be logically correct, intellectually clear, beautiful in structure, and purposeful in direction.

The correctness, clarity, purity, logic, effectiveness, and purposefulness of speech are the most important requirements placed on it.

The correctness of speech is its most important communicative quality.

Because if speech is not correct, its other communicative qualities, namely logic, clarity, and purposefulness, are also impaired.

For speech to be correct, strict adherence to two norms is required - stress and grammatical norms. It is natural that these two important components of a teacher's oral speech rise to the level of the main criteria determining his oratory skills. The biggest flaw in a teacher's speech is the incorrect use of stress in the expression of terms and terms, concepts and phrases.

By observing grammatical norms, we mean the correct use of the rules of sentence construction, the avoidance of errors in adding roots and suffixes, the use of consonant suffixes in their place, the correspondence of the possessive and participle, the regularities of their connection with them. Clarity is one of the communicative qualities of speech, which is manifested as the correspondence of the content of speech with objective reality.

Creating a clear speech requires the speaker to: a) know the synonymous possibilities of the language and use them in speech, distinguishing the necessary from the synonymous series; b) know the meanings of the word used in speech in all its aspects; c) pay serious attention to the polysemy of the word, clearly imagine which side of its meaning is intended when a polysemous word is used in speech, and consider whether other sides of the word interfere with the emergence of thought; d) know the characteristics of homonyms, since ignorance of them leads to a violation of clarity; d) knowing paronyms, paying attention to their sound similarities; f) introducing into speech, with a good understanding of the meanings of words used in a narrow environment, foreign, professional, archaic, obsolete, dialectisms.

When it comes to the purity of speech, we mean, first of all, its compliance with the norms of the literary language. The purity of our speech is mainly affected by the following: 1. Words, phrases, as well as grammatical forms, pronunciation and accent of words and word combinations characteristic of local dialects and dialects. 2. Inappropriately used foreign words and word combinations. 3. Jargon. 4. Vulgarisms. 5. "Parasite" words that are excessively repeated in speech. 6. Office-related terms. 7. Barbarisms.

The inappropriate use of the above dulls both everyday speech and artistic speech. Each teacher should strive to ensure that his speech is at the level of literary standards. The unnecessary introduction of language tools characteristic of his dialect into speech also distorts speech. However, dialectisms and barbarisms can perform a certain artistic and aesthetic function in the language of a literary work, and can also serve to implement a certain idea or intention of the author. Words from other languages that are used inappropriately in speech are called barbarisms. Jargon is words and phrases that representatives of a certain group use in order to distinguish themselves from the majority with their speech,

giving them their own meaning. Vulgarisms are coarse words or phrases (such as swearing, insulting, rudeness, ignorance). Lexical units called parasitic words are also alien to the culture of the language. They are mainly used in colloquial speech, appear as a result of the speaker's inattention and inattention to his own speech, and gradually become a habit.

The logicity of a teacher's speech is closely related to its main qualities - correctness and accuracy. Because it is natural that both a grammatically incorrect speech and an unsuccessfully selected lexical unit for expressing a thought lead to a violation of logic. When it comes to the effectiveness of a teacher's speech, the process of oral speech is primarily meant. Accordingly, the psychological situation in which the speech is perceived by the listener is also taken into account. That is, in this case, the speaker must control the audience, starting from their level of knowledge and even age, and how his speech is perceived. Just as it is not advisable to speak in a simple, simple language in front of people with professional knowledge, it is also not advisable to try to speak in a scientific and official language in front of ordinary, insufficiently educated listeners. The teacher should always speak with the understanding that the suitability of the speech for the audience is its most important quality indicator. Speaking in a language that the audience can understand and convincing them of the idea being expressed are among the main conditions set before teachers. For this, as mentioned above, in addition to knowing the educational material and its content and essence well, there must also be a clear, defined plan for its presentation.

The teacher's attitude to his speech is also an important professional quality. This situation effectively serves to strengthen the connection between the teacher and the audience. If the speaker tries to prove his ideas based on examples from his own or the listeners' lives, if he expresses his subjective thoughts on the topic, the speech will be even more convincing and effective. Metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, simile, epithet, repetition and literary devices, which are considered figurative means of language, also play a significant role in achieving the effectiveness of the speech. In addition, to ensure effectiveness in speech, it is necessary to use proverbs, sayings, wise words and expressions, especially phraseological units. The purposefulness of speech is very important. Speech culture means mastering the norms of the literary language and using them fully in speech. Language is a tool of communication, a mirror of life, a sign of spirituality, and at the same time serves as the most important methodological tool for the teacher. Language is also the factor that distinguishes man from the animal world and turns him into the lord and crown of the universe. The highest products of human intellectual activity, the "fruits" of thought, are revealed through language and speech. The historical, cultural, and spiritual service of speech is, of course, unlimited. However, the possibilities of language are

revealed through speech, in the process of speech, and teachers must use these possibilities effectively. If speech is of poor quality, the unlimited possibilities of language will not be sufficiently revealed in the educational process. As one of the philosophers of Fap6, R. Emerson, emphasized, "Speech is a powerful force: it convinces, encourages, and compels." This saying emphasizes the virtue of speech, which is, first of all, the art of persuasion. A teacher communicating with students must speak convincingly, his speech must be well-founded and well-founded. Only a teacher who has earned the trust and love of students can be called a true teacher. Speech is language in action. Speech logically connects language units and sets them in motion. Speech consists of words, word combinations, and phrases.

Speech and speech etiquette are the main criteria that determine a person's spirituality and enlightenment. So, a person's etiquette is, first of all, reflected in his speech. Speech etiquette means conveying the messages that need to be said, respecting the listener, and using expressions that are in accordance with literary norms. Even bad news can be conveyed to the listener without harming him. To do this, the speaker must have a perfect knowledge of the language. Gentle, pleasant, and polite speech does not come by itself. It is achieved by imitating exemplary people from a young age, learning from them, practicing regularly, and taking the language seriously. The best example for a student is a teacher. The teacher should always feel this. The child should also be taught the etiquette of expressing gratitude in a timely manner to those who have done him good, fulfilled the task, or fulfilled the request. There are beautiful expressions in our language that express encouragement and gratitude. Introducing them into everyday life and using them in their proper place will greatly enhance a person's character. The teacher should encourage students who have completed the assignment well with sweet and pleasant words.

The level of culture of the teacher, how much he has been educated by studying, is evident from his written and oral speech.

High demands are also made on the teacher's written speech. These include spelling literacy, fluent expression of thought in writing, adherence to writing rules, and the avoidance of spelling, punctuation, and stylistic errors. Therefore, the teacher's written speech is said to consist of two components - spelling literacy and husnihat (calligraphy, writing style).

Oral and written perfect speech are also conditionally (figuratively) called the two "bright faces" of the teacher. Despite the fact that language performs a number of tasks, such as knowing the world, collecting knowledge, preserving it, conveying it to the next generations, reflecting spiritual relationships, and realizing the categories of beauty, its main function is to ensure communication between people and is a powerful tool in their acquisition of knowledge.

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